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Non-human companionship: Practicing free improvisation through interaction with machines

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***Abstract.** Free improvisation is a musical genre that defies traditional forms of music-making, defining itself by its absences. This creates a particular environment that imposes challenges to those trying to learn it and to educators inspired to teach it. Generally, ensemble practice is considered to be the most suitable and widely accepted method for practicing the genre. Nevertheless, should it be the only one? This article discusses the different approaches to learning improvisation and particularly free improvisation, proposing the use of interactive musical systems as a possible alternative to the problem. To do so, we present a custom-designed improvisation machine as a model example and a preliminary evaluation done with it.*

1. Introduction

After more than five decades of continuous practice, free improvisation still enjoys a curious position in the world of music: it's often misunderstood by other musicians, largely ignored by the general public, and deeply loved by a small sample of listeners and practitioners. Free improvisation can be best defined by its processes and intentions rather than its sonic output [Borgo 2022, 167], [Stenström 2009, 105] [Hickey 2009, 294], flourishing from the desire to be a universal form of music making, which borrows stones from each player's cultural background as its means to construct a new house for each performance. One can probably come up with some musical analysis to explain how a particular performance was built and which materials sustain it, although this analysis will probably not be useful when applied to future performances.

Unlike most music genres, which typically rely on fixed compositions, free improvisation is conceived as spontaneous creations, and differently from other types of music which do employ improvised material, the musical form and the development of a freely improvised piece is done in real-time, with no settled prior references (such as motifs, melodies, or chord progressions). Nevertheless, having no predetermined structure does not mean its practitioners have no preparation for public performance: most of them have found a way to establish themselves as improvisers, and as we will see further in the paper, this is generally thought to be achieved by repeated ensemble practice.

But how does a musician with no access to fellow improvisers can accomplish some degree of proficiency in this particular genre? This article exposes the first steps in a research that addresses this particular issue, proposing the use of improvising machines

as a possible solution. The study was conducted with the development of a prototype for an improvising machine, designed for this particular musical purpose, and evaluated in a preliminary, informal setting.

Improvising machines are a type of musical agent [Tatar and Pasquier 2019] designed for the task of live improvisation, typically in interaction with a musician. The development of such systems has been a recurring topic in computer music research, dating back to the pioneering work of George Lewis in the 80's [Lewis 2000]. The theme has spawned interest both in musicians and programmers, and has evolved to utilize various computational methods that reflect the musical and cultural backgrounds of their designers, ranging from complex rule-based systems to modern artificial neural network projects [Tatar and Pasquier 2019].

Engenhoca, a prototype for an improvising machine, is presented here for the first time as ongoing research that investigates a potential solution for individuals who wish to practice free improvisation alone. The project is distributed as free and open-source software (FOSS) and was originally initiated as an undergraduate thesis in music education. It is currently being further developed as part of a Master's research project. A technical description of the system and a preliminary evaluation will be presented, along with plans for its future development.

2. Pedagogical methods for musical improvisation

To begin our discussion on the position of improvisation in music education, we could first understand it as a musical skill analogous to spontaneous speech [Johnson-Laird 2002, 417]. This analogy, repeatedly employed by improvisers and researchers in the field [Dobbins 1980] [Burton 2010] [Berkowitz 2016], is defended by many as a justification for the necessity of learning to improvise, framing improvisation as a fundamental musical skill that is necessary for demonstrating creative ability in music. Under this perspective, a professional musician with proficiency in score reading who does not know how to improvise would appear as an adult who could read sophisticated poetry (and maybe write some too) while still not being able to sustain a dialogue [Dobbins 1980, 37].

The case for improvisation could also be sustained by the fact that most music performed and listened to is based on improvised genres, making a compelling case for, at least, the presence of improvisation in general musical training. The paradox appears when music education curricula do the opposite of what would be expected, with almost no space at all for improvisation courses in Western education [Sawyer 2007].

The development of pedagogical methods for improvisation has been analyzed by Pressing (1987) and summarized in five historical stages by Hickey (2009) : embellishment (1), patterns and models (2), problem-solving (3), play-by-ear (4), and free improvisation (5). In pre-Baroque times (1), improvisation was considered a “real-time composition” and was limited to variation and embellishment techniques. The use of patterns and models (2) from the 17th and 18th centuries, such as figured bass and Italian Partimento, find parallels with approaches based on imitation of melodic patterns from the 20th century. Problem-solving (3) exercises (pioneered by Jaques-Dalcroze) require technique and expressiveness of the students, with profound attention to their individuality. Methods focused on transcribing from recordings or teacher's performances (4) require students to infer which decisions to make in different musical situations. A humanistic point of view

is observed in modern approaches based on creativity and individual expression concepts (5), inspired by the work of Orff, Kodaly, Suzuki, Jaques-Dalcroze, and Schafer.

More recent approaches to music education have followed technological developments of the digital age, making use of a variety of available software to enhance the acquisition of a number of musical skills¹. For instance, Fern (1995) proposes a computer program to teach jazz improvisation, using Miles Davis' 1954 recording of the tune *Four* as a transcribed reference for students and a chord-scale² method as a guide to creating new improvised lines. With the advent of the World Wide Web, some educators have turned to social media platforms such as YouTube as a means of sharing instructional material with a broader audience at little to no cost. Unsurprisingly, the platform has been used to teach musical improvisation, with a diverse range of methods employed, e.g. theory related to improvisation practices, performance transcriptions, technical exercises, and play-along videos, making it one of the most prominent ways in which the Web has contributed to the task. Finally, Frankel (2010) notices that even though musicians demonstrate pioneerism in the adoption of new technologies, there appears to be a continued reluctance among music educators to embrace technological tools for instruction.

3. Challenges to teach free improvisation

One might notice that most modern approaches to improvised music cited before belong specifically to the language of jazz, and that could be explained by its popularity among improvised musical genres, as well by the fact it consists of a musical idiom with approachable boundaries for harmonic, rhythmic and melodic discourses.

Returning to Johnson-Laird's analogy between musical improvisation and spontaneous speech, how does it fit free improvisation, a form of improvised discourse that does not belong to any specific idiom, does not adhere to any kind of syntactic rules nor uses any predetermined vocabulary? As Derek Bailey notes, it "has no stylistic or idiomatic commitment. It has no prescribed idiomatic sound. The characteristics of freely improvised music are established only by the sonic-musical identity of the person or persons playing it" [Bailey 1993, 83]. This paradigm doesn't find a parallel in spoken language, making evident the challenge to formulate methodologies for free improvisation education capable of attending to so many absences. This situation could explain why Borgo (2022, 9) presumes you would incur a passionate argument when asking an improviser if it can be taught. One way or another, the history of the genre has provided many examples of improvisers inspired to do so [Lange 2011].

A less idealist view on free improvisation "language" is offered by Menezes (2010, 15), when pointing out that practitioners of the genre do find their own boundaries shaped by their technical constraints and their personal database of experiences. And as even Borgo (2002, 184) indicates, there have been identifiable characteristics in the output of the genre in the last decades of its practice, with a shared range of "techniques, approaches and clichés" [Menezes 2010, 16], although not explicitly specified by the au-

¹An extensive list of examples in various categories can be seen in Nart (2016). Fein (2017) presents an introduction to some of these tools, such as auto-accompaniment, notation, and music production software, explaining ways they could be used to complement jazz education in private, classroom, or lab settings.

²"Chord-scale" is a conventional designation for several methods in jazz education that associate chords found in a musical piece to specific musical scales to be employed in an improvisation.

thors. Thus, the absence of rigid characteristics in free improvisation does not necessarily imply a complete lack of boundaries.

Furthermore, one could argue the idiom of a particular performance and its set of rules is developed on the spot as an implicit agreement between the musicians, that “should be able to select the proper constraints in the course of the piece, rather than being dependent on precisely chosen ones” (Ann Farber apud [Belgrad 1999]). Under this perspective, a freely improvised piece should not employ prearranged material, but the decisions made by each player can shape the musical boundaries of the performance.

This context helps us to understand why free improvisation is seen to be dependent on interaction with other musicians, with collective engagement being accepted as the most fruitful context for it. For instance, Bailey presents that improvisation “although a vehicle for self-expression, is about playing with other people and some of the greatest opportunities provided by free improvisation are in the exploration of relationships between players” [Bailey 1993, 105]. In a complementary way, Tom Hall believes that when “more than one person is involved, improvisation is as much about the relationship between what’s played as it is about what each person is playing” [Hall 2009].

Even though Bailey (1993, 105) asserts that the majority of improvisers explore the option of performing alone, Corbett (2016, 119) suggests that there is a certain skepticism regarding solo playing and raises the question of whether it might be more accurately viewed as real-time composition. Corbett’s argument highlights the importance of interaction in free improvisation, implying that instead of interacting with other players, a solo improviser can engage with their instrument, the performance space, or the audience, a perspective that could be well integrated with Ubimus’ technologies and practices.

To address those difficulties and particularities of the genre, approaches to the practice of free improvisation often emphasize the significance of ensemble practices. This approach draws parallels with language learning focused on conversation, emphasizing the importance of interaction to the genre. Stenström (2009, 38) defends the ensemble practice approach, arguing that solo playing may not provide the most solid foundation for ensemble improvisation, as the latter relies heavily on the musical interplay and interaction among its participants.

Although the argument for the importance of ensemble practice can be restrictive under a broader notion of creative models, free improvisation figures itself as a genre that, like Ubimus practices, should not limit musical diversity, which is exemplified by the increasing presence of musicians with varied backgrounds coming into the genre in the latest decades [Borgo 2022, 5]. Free improvisation also incorporates some of the same aspects of musical creation adopted by Ubimus³, such as the focus on the creative *process* instead of the musical *product*, and an anti-formalist approach to music making that embraces and deals with the presence of technological and environmental resources and the participation of the audience.

Hall (2009) offers an alternative method to learn free improvisation, compiling exercises, and warm-ups that cover practices for groups, duets, and even solo playing. The book first presents his philosophy of improvisation and ideas for approaching its practice, which is later followed by dozens of exercises subdivided into thematic chapters. His

³See [Keller et al. 2014] for further discussion on the topic.

teaching seems to be preoccupied with the awareness needed for improvisers to accomplish fluid interactions and subtle explorations of the sound materials employed during a performance. The themes employed in each chapter explore distinct musical parameters or musical concepts such as melody and accompaniment, textures, groove, silence, and so on. Hall suggests, with examples, that the exercises can be combined to offer new possibilities for practice.

Methods used to teach free jazz can be valuable alternatives to learning free improvisation, even though both genres are not always considered as the same thing⁴ [Corbett 2016, 17]. Crook (2006) offers a guide to learning free jazz (also referred to as free improvisation in the book) by departing from the understanding of conventional jazz. For him, one must be familiar with what he is *freeing himself from* to be truly *free*. Later on, the book demonstrates how improvisation can be organized when the elements of time and changes (musical pulse and chord progressions) are absent.

Vesisenaho et al. (2017) present a framework for the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) for creativity related to improvisation. They argue that such technologies have the potential to introduce new possibilities for learning environments and their associated use with mobile networking could allow those experiences to take place in diverse educational settings. Under this premise, Clemente et al. (2020) conducted a series of experiments with ICT and Ubiquitous Computing in a gaming format to support free improvisation practices with an ensemble of saxophone, observing improvements in the sonority of the group, according to the students and teachers who participated in the experiments.

Barbara Lange (2011) noted that improvisers' educational values, as expressed in workshops she attended, align with Paulo Freire's educational principles that form the basis of Ubimus dialogics, which highlight "the role of the horizontal exchanges among group members, the respect for cultural diversity and the adoption of a positive attitude toward local knowledge" [Keller et al. 2020, 9]. However, Lange also observed that free improvisation workshops frequently revolve around a teacher figure who imparts information in a one-way direction, replicating the banking model that Freire criticized.

3.1. Machine improvisation as a valuable approach

For several decades, most people had not encountered any serious problems gathering together to practice most music genres. This scenario changed in 2020 due to measures taken in most countries to reduce the spread of the new coronavirus, with lockdowns having a brutal impact on people's ability to gather and play music together. Alternatives to in-person practice were explored during the period, with low-latency network communication being demonstrated as a somewhat promising solution for the task, even in contexts that demanded precise synchronous interaction [Bosi et al. 2021]. Playing remotely over the internet has been a practice in Ubimus even before the pandemic [Schiavoni et al. 2019], suggesting this can be a reasonable solution to bring together musicians to perform improvised music despite being physically separated. Software applications that enable remote communication or perhaps Internet forums dedicated to the practice could facilitate the assemblage of like-minded free improvisation enthusiasts interested in practicing from home.

⁴A distinction that has been criticized, see [Banerji 2021].

However, this approach still heavily depends upon live interaction, and as others have noticed, the inclination towards synchronicity may not be in UbiMus's practices best interest, especially in cases with "uneven levels of musical training" as pedagogical situations may impose [Keller et al. 2020, 4]. Thus, one may inquire if live interaction is needed for a freely improvised music session to occur. Dynamics that differ from synchronized performances could bring a new dimension to the experience, providing different ways to think about it and making room for new pedagogical concepts that may arise from such scenarios.

Additionally, it is remarkable that ensemble practice in nearly every genre of music is not to be considered the only source of training in a specific style. Most genres that function around a fixed composition employ repetition and memorization as part of training that should be performed alone. In contrast, when accounting for technical exercises, there is not much left for practitioners of free improvisation to explore while unaccompanied, and as we have seen above, solo playing does not provide much ground for the development of the interaction skills needed for the genre.

Researchers on interactive musical systems have long been interested in the potential applications of their innovations, ranging from education to different stages of creative practice. The underlying premise is that designing and engaging with such systems can yield valuable insights into our musicality [Rowe 2001, 3]. George Lewis, a leading figure in the field of improvising machines and a pioneer in research in this area, shares the conviction that these systems can help us understand the inner workings of music, and particularly of improvisation. For Lewis, the ability of machines to improvise provides us with a unique opportunity to gain insight into the mechanics of musical meaning [Lewis 2018, 5]. Lewis also argues that the act of developing such machines is a type of musical discourse that goes beyond the conventions of Western music practice [Lewis 1999, 108], questioning the model of musical interaction conceptualized on the passiveness of computer programs merely thought as instruments, in conformity with UbiMus concepts [Keller et al. 2020, 5].

After these considerations, we propose the use of improvising machines as a valuable approach to the practice of free improvisation without human companionship, believing it should serve as an alternative to ensemble playing, mimicking the companion of other improvisers or even providing a different kind of interaction than what is possible with human company.

4. Engenhoca

To address this idea, research has been conducted on the development of a prototype for an improvising machine, named *Engenhoca*, a Brazilian Portuguese jargon for a machine built in an improvised manner. The prototype is capable of generating music expected to be properly fitted in the context of free improvisation. *Engenhoca* is a rule-based⁵ transformative system⁶ that mirrors musical concepts and personal aesthetic preferences

⁵Rule-based refers to systems that execute predetermined actions in case some scenario or condition is met. The algorithms used in each system can vary greatly and are associated with the design preferences of its authors [Tatar and Pasquier 2019].

⁶Transformative systems refer to computer-based systems that manipulate existing musical material through various transformations to create new musical sentences, which may or may not be recognized as originated from the original material [Rowe 1992, 7].

of the author [Barros 2021]. The system analyzes incoming sounds played by a musician; decides what to play and whether or not to play; and finally synthesizes and outputs audio in real time. The system tries to derive its musicality from the musician it is playing along with, while also avoiding imitation or conformity, which provides it with a sense of agency and independence.

Engenhoca was entirely programmed in Pure Data (Pd)⁷, a FOSS application, easily accessible by other musicians who might be interested in developing the system's core functionalities. To facilitate this, *Engenhoca* is also distributed as FOSS⁸, allowing its code to be studied, executed, shared, and modified. We believe that this type of software distribution resonates with the principles of improvisation pedagogy, and with the very idea of what freedom is.

4.1. Technical description

The basic architecture of the system is subdivided into three main subpatches⁹, responsible for different musical tasks: audio analysis (1), decision-making (2), and audio output (3). The separation between tasks makes it possible to implement a full range of audio synthesizers or MIDI instruments that can be controlled by the decision-making process.

The system settings can be controlled through a graphical interface, with controls designed to manage signal gain, calculate note offset amplitude (defining what is silence and what is sound), and select the type of output (digital audio synthesis or MIDI messages). The interface also offers simple oscilloscopes and volume meters for the audio input and the audio output.

Engenhoca works straightforwardly, analyzing the audio input with a diverse range of musical information retrieval algorithms, then segmenting and classifying them into musical phrases and types of sound events (1). This analysis is used by the system to make musical decisions (2) in two levels: an orchestration of the number of different voices playing, and each note's characteristics (duration, pitch, intensity, timbre, and octave), later on grouped into musical phrases and sent to virtual players (3), which can execute them through digital audio synthesis or MIDI messages.

The input analysis (1) subpatch is capable of discerning different characteristics of timbre, pitch, attack, rhythm, articulation, dynamics, and phrasing of incoming audio. Some higher-level algorithms were implemented directly in Pd, while others use Pd's native solutions or objects from the external library *timbreID*¹⁰. A representation of this subpatch can be seen below (see Figure 1).

The decision-making (2) subpatch is subdivided into two main processes: an orchestration subpatch that decides how many voices should be playing, and different subpatches for each voice (comprehending five independent monophonic virtual players). The decision on when to open and when to close a voice output is made by a series of calculations based on the musical activity of the incoming audio. The opening or closing

⁷Pure Data (Pd) is a visual programming language for multimedia designed by Miller Puckette. For more information, visit <http://msp.ucsd.edu/> or <https://puredata.info/>.

⁸Available at <https://github.com/ofefo/engenhoca>.

⁹Applications developed with Pd are usually referred to as patches and organized into subpatches, in a logic that might resemble a cabinet with different drawers, each containing different functions or algorithms.

¹⁰For more information regarding this library, see [Brent 2010].

Figure 1. Dataflow representation of the audio analysis subpatch. The incoming audio is analyzed by different subpatches that measure the musical or sonic attributes of each phrase played by the musician it interacts with. The onset and offset of a musical event play an important role in defining when to listen to new attributes.

of a voice is allowed when intensity, intervallic relationships, or rhythmic data from what is being played changes drastically when compared to the last phrases heard by the system. The characteristics of each note that will be played are defined separately by each voice subpatch, selecting meaningful elements of musical input and performing varied transformations on it.

Rhythmic transformations are applied over a list of inter-onset intervals (IOI) extracted from the input, generating musical phrases with different sizes that vary in response to the average IOI duration of the last phrase played by the human. Examples of operations done are inversion, *ostinato*, rotation, shuffling, addition (in allusion to the added value rhythm process described in [Messiaen 1944, 16]), and multiplication (following Stockhausen's scale of duration [Stockhausen 1957], constrained by the duration range found in the incoming rhythm).

In a similar way, pitch transformations are applied over pitch sets that are extracted from the input. When no discernible pitch is identified in the input, the output also tends towards more percussive timbres, using the Spectral Centroid as a reference for pitch. The pitch operations are analogous to those described above for rhythm, but happen to be in a melodic context, in a style similar to what is commonly used when composing serial atonal music. Examples of operations are sorting, sorting followed by inversion, transposition, and multiplication. These same operations can be done to their complementary set [Forte 1973, 209], providing further harmonic contrast.

The output of the system (3) works in two different forms: a digital audio synthesizer and MIDI messages. The audio output consists of a Frequency Modulation

synthesizer as described by Chowning (1973) , routed through stereo spatialization and a Schroeder reverberator [Schroeder 1962], allowing a somewhat diverse sonic output. However, as we will address later, this has been shown to be aesthetically insufficient for extended use of the system. The MIDI messages provide the user an opportunity to use their own solution for sonic output. The audio input and the output are automatically recorded as raw files for each session.

4.2. Preliminary evaluation

The system was once evaluated in an informal manner, providing some modest feedback for the ongoing phase in which improvements are being made as part of a Master's research. We invited three undergraduate music students who had previous experience in free improvisation ensemble practice to play with the system for about a week, making recordings and observations of their experience. The evaluation was done in an interview format, with two open-ended questions about their experience with the system and perspectives about using similar software as a practice tool for free improvisation.

When asked about the system, problems recognized by the participants included the feeling their timbres were “repetitive” and their responses “not natural” or “random”. One participant indicated that it was difficult to find an “endpoint” to the improvisation, and trying to “force it to react” in a desired way ultimately failed. When asked about the prospects of improvising machines as a practice tool, one of the students indicated that he finds it an “interesting resource”, however, he “was not confident” about the aesthetical results of the interaction. Another participant had a “positive evaluation”, but also thought the interaction to be more “difficult” than those with humans. The third participant saw “potential” for the idea, but felt the “lack of a corporeal presence” as a downside to the interaction¹¹.

The current evaluation of the system indicates that there is a general positivity towards the idea of improvising with a machine as a practice tool in free improvisation studies. However, since it was done with a small number of participants, informally interviewed, it is unclear whether its results show any real significance to the theme.

5. Discussion and future perspectives

As we have seen, pedagogy for improvised music genres has varied throughout music history, providing us with a range of possible approaches when we desire to teach them today. However, free improvisation presents some unique challenges to musicians and educators trying to work with it, as there's no correct way to approach it and it might not share an explicit musical vocabulary as found in other improvised genres.

To overcome these particularities, most improvisers accept ensemble practice as the most suitable method for practicing the genre. This research debates whether there's no alternative to ensemble practice in this context, observing different approaches for free improvisation education found in the literature, as well as suggesting technology-assisted practices such as network communications and the use of interactive musical systems as possible substitutes that conform with UbiMus' practices. Finally, we present *Engenhoca*, a custom-designed improvising machine under ongoing development. The project aims

¹¹Audio demonstrations of interactions with the system can be accessed at: <https://archive.org/details/engenhoca>.

to demonstrate how such machines could be implemented, by distributing it as a FOSS application and permitting other musicians to modify the application for their particular musical goals and preferences.

As seen above, a noticeable problem in the interaction with the system lies in the lack of timbre variety. This was an expected opinion since the beginning of the development and can be explained by the simplicity of the audio synthesis methods used. As *sound* itself might be considered the basic unit in free improvisation [Hall 2009], a significant improvement to be made is to guarantee a broader sound scope for the system. Also, the perception of their responses being random might indicate the need for further improvements in the approach to interaction.

We expect to provide future insights into the pedagogical use of such systems by developing and evaluating them further. Moreover, to reach its goal of a viable pedagogical tool, we expect to provide *Engenhoca* with different functionalities that could help this ambition. Discussed ideas are statistical analysis of musical data that has been played and network communication connection that could enable different modes of interaction.

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